
Impact of Globalization on English Language in India

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Abstract

This paper attempts to discuss the prominence of English in India in the light of globalized world. 'Globalization' in its literal sense is the process of transformation of regional phenomena into global ones. In this process people in the world are unified into single society and function together.

The word 'Globalization' acquired a great prominence especially in the twentieth century. The whole world is indisputably in the clutches of globalization, privatization and liberalization. The word 'globalization' has left an everlasting impression on the aspects of economics, politics and culture. As a result many dramatic changes could transparently be seen in the language as well. Globalization created plethora of fast-track opportunities. The phenomenon has accelerated the technological advancements and innovations which made English as the language of science and technology.

The prominence of English language is rapidly increasing day by day. English became Link language and library language. English was recognized as the official associate language in India. English has acquired the status of the language of administration; trade, commerce, judiciary and the medium of instruction in universities and colleges during the globalization since Indian language were completely undermined during the British rule.

English booms in literary areas like Indian writing in English and in intellectual areas like Indian culture and philosophy, post-colonial studies. There is an international market for English and materials in English in print as well as electronic media; newspapers, news magazines. Mass media, information technology and communication have brought about radical changes in national and international contexts. These changes took place due to globalization. As a result India is compelled to catch up with the west. Therefore, English in India became a prominent language.

English bridges the gap between many global issues unlike other languages in the world. It is firmly believed that English is a language that could unite the world and spread global consciousness.

Keywords: Globalization, English Language Teaching, communication, second language, foreign language.

Introduction

Globalization describes the political, economic, and cultural atmosphere of today. We live in an intensely interdependent world in which all the earth's people with their immense differences of culture and historical experience are compressed together in instant communication through 'globalization'. Globalization has had a huge impact on thinking across the humanities, redefining the understanding of fields such as communication, culture, politics and literature. This also challenged the prejudice to hear the dissident voices of Indian, African and South American authors sidelined for long. English Language education should teach about issues that cross national boundaries, and interconnected systems. Globalization and technological advancements in India are increasing access to the world and subsequently English Language and Literature should reflect this global outlook. In the recent years English has been chosen as the major foreign language taught in all educational institutions. Globalization's impact on literature is manifold, with both positive and negative associations. The themes of Hybridity and Multi-rootedness- in part, expressions of the subjective experience of globalization-are increasingly prevalent in diasporic literary text besides shaping new literary forms and translations.

Globalisation provides innovative solutions to the challenges and fostering a growing awareness of enhances processes of, cross-fertilisation and multinational culture leading to new dimensions in Indian Diaspora literature. Indian women writers like Chitra Banerjee, Jhumpa Lahiri unveiled the complexities of discrimination and assimilation, social and demographic changes due to immigration, which not only led to many conflicts in domestic lives of men and women but also affected the society at large. Kiran Desai's 'The Inheritance of Loss' has been widely hailed as the quintessential post-colonial novel. It is a bold, frontal and multi-pronged attack on the discourse and practices of colonialism. Globalisation eliminated the barriers to trade, communication and cultural exchange including wealth. Local traditions of knowledge that resist globalization, cultural nativism, notions and specific national identity need to be kept alive in Indian English Writing, thus creating a post colonial space which will not be dominated or obliterated by cyberspace. It's most difficult to capture 'nationhood' in the modern globalised literature. To even think about literature and globalization is to push against deeply held traditions. Under the globalised circumstances, English no longer belongs to the British, but has diversified into various national/local versions, of which Indian English is one. As English is a market force today, the teaching of English as a language needs to be tailored to fit the requirements of the global market. English translations of works in Indian languages must be given significant space. It would serve a dual purpose: of knitting Indian literatures together within India and of making this body of work accessible globally.

Translation as an architect of authority and reality has a long history, and it is possible to apply this viewpoint to how translation impacts globalization. Language, in fact, is usually the first thing about a subjugated culture that the conquerors attempt to take from them.

As companies internationalize and enter global markets, operational issues affected by language inevitably come forth. In response to transcultural challenges of intra-organizational communication that arise from coordination of a multinational workforce, companies often adopt a policy of linguistic assimilation by imposing a common language to be used throughout the organization. A global marketplace suggests a need for skills in a multiplicity of languages. However, the globalization has given rise to a rapid increase in the use of English by companies. Twenty five percent world's population speaks English, and it's the official

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language of more than fifty countries. Because of its significance and prominence Multi National Companies adopted English as the common language of business.

Majority of the writers have explored the reasons for the spread of English across the globe and have conceptualized methods of teaching English to a non native who would be using English as the second language. There has been profound thinking about how to address the issues of English language varieties, to identify differences stemming from the varieties and to establish standardized Global English.

Braj Kachru (*The hand book of world Englishes*, *World Englishes: Critical concepts in linguistics*).

He surveys the extent of Global English's use around the world and briefly outlines the history of its spread. Also examines nineteenth century ideas about the place of English in the world and foundations for its success laid by the British Empire and Industrial revolution. He goes on to describe the cultural legacy that underpins the present dominance of English its use in diplomacy and international business affairs, in the media, education and on the internet.

'The hand book of world Englishes' represents the cross-cultural and international contextualization of the English language and the contributions articulate the visions of scholars from major varieties of world Englishes: African, Asian, European, and North and South American.

The new global economy of the twenty-first century has transformed the economic, social, educational and political landscape in a profound and indelible manner. It is composed a trilogy of interactive forces that include globalization, trade liberalization and information technology. globalization has melted national borders, free trade has enhanced economic integration. English language has become a vehicle of Business communication. Writers like David Crystal and others have wondered how such a dramatic linguistic shift has taken place in less than a lifetime. It has impacted every domain of education, business, technology, research and every sphere of human engagement.

Some linguists feel that the spread of English is because of the play of Power and Politics that have caused the spread of English across the globe and predict that the rise of English spells out doom for other native languages.

As Fishman puts in his conclusion to the work *Post-imperial English*...

For the foreseeable future, Global arrangements will increasingly make use of English while local life between locals will increasingly be attached to national languages and cultures, each complementing the other by satisfying different needs and granting satisfactions associated with modern existence. (Fishman et al.640).

This contends the imperialistic language view expressed by people like Phillipson and specifies the special role of a Global language which is duly supported by David Crystal and Braj Kachru in the various works.

English is one of the fastest growing languages, but in different linguistic incarnations. While even the native speakers of English use different dialects and accents, the non-native speakers of English use many more varieties of English or Englishes. Most experts would grant that today non-native users of English far outnumber native users of English, raising various questions concerning English education, testing and its use in business and cross-cultural communication.

Conclusion

Globalization is most often understood purely as economic agenda because of its economic interests and socio-political ideologies seeking to re-enact colonialism. Proficiency in English has been identified as the stepping stone to success in many Asian countries. Acculturation and “nativization” has made it endearing to the people who sue such varies. The use and status of English is inextricably linked to the broader social, cultural, economic, political situation of the globalised world. The current high use and status of English in various nations is going to yield better results and the allegations of it being the killer language is unfounded as it has in many ways given to the native language protection movement across the globe. Considering the scope of international communication and the surge of information, it is discernible that the English language will continue to hold prestigious position. This process is not reversible as in the case of Latin. Latin became dead because it lacked English-like flexibility and science documentation. Now that everything is recorded in English language it is evident that learning English for international, national, local communication will surely yield benefits.

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